

Average Plate: Usage

Every day, around 100 billion WhatsApp messages and 4.75 billion Snaps are sent worldwide, and 3.6 billion Facebook posts and 1.3 billion Instagram posts are created. [14-21].

- 5 blocks
- 5 blocks
- 3 blocks

The most popular social networks in Germany are YouTube and WhatsApp [13].

- 3 blocks
- 1 block

In Germany, 50% of all social media users follow influencers. Among those under 40, the number is even higher at 91% [22, 23].

- 1 block

87% of people in Germany use social media, on average 99 minutes per day [3-12].

- 107 km per year (3 blocks)
- 416 min per year (3 blocks)
- 3:22 min per year (3 blocks)

Mobile-data communications represent approximately 6% of total data traffic in Germany [24].

- 1 block
- 1 block

CO₂: 17 blocks

H₂O: 15 blocks

Only about 42% of 16-64 years old use cloud storage [41].

- 1 block
- 1 block

Approximately 4 search queries are made per person each day in Germany [47-51].

- < 1 km per year (0 blocks)

In Germany, approximately 30 emails and 19 text messages are sent per person each day [42-46].

- 15 km per year (0 blocks)
- < 1 min per year (0 blocks)

working conditions: 13 blocks

On average, each person in Germany listens to 39 minutes of audio content in real time (streaming) [25-30].

- 4.1 km per year (0 blocks)
- 2:50 min per year (0 blocks)
- 1 block

On average, each person in Germany watches 45 minutes of video content in real time (streaming) [25, 30-33].

- 82 km per year (1 block)
- 136 min per year (1 block)

Full HD (1080p) is the default setting for most streaming providers [34-37].

- 3 blocks
- 3 blocks

The average Android user spends around 4:19 minutes per day playing video games on their smartphone [25-27, 38-40].

- < 1 km per year (0 blocks)
- < 1 min per year (0 blocks)

Around 60% of people in Germany use generative AI at least once a month, and around 6% use it every day [50-55].

- < 1 km per year (0 blocks)
- < 1 min per year (0 blocks)
- 5 blocks